

Solvent Effect on the Kinetics of the Reaction of 2,3-[Cyclopenten-3',5'-diyl]-endo-N-(2'',4''-dinitrophenoxy)succinimide with Morpholine

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Recently we carried out kinetic studies on the *endo*- and the *exo*-isomers of the title compound with hydroxide ion and piperidine in aqueous acetonitrile (1 : 4, v/v) at 35 ± 0.1° and reported¹ catalysis by base in both the cases. Similar observations were also reported² with other substrate. We also studied³ the reactions of the title compound with another cyclic amine, morpholine in the same solvent and noted absence of catalysis in this medium. As the mechanism of aromatic nucleophilic substitution is affected by media, we further investigated the reactions of the *endo*-isomer (1) with morpholine in acetonitrile, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, benzene and toluene, the results are presented.

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

The various kinetic data are given in Table 1. The second order rate constants (k_A) obtained by dividing the first order rate constants (k_o) by [morpholine], were insensitive to morpholine concentration, indicating absence of

base catalysis. A plot of k_A vs [morpholine] is linear with a negligible slope. The formation of an intermediate complex (T_1) is rate-determining as shown in Scheme 1. Due to the presence of electronegative oxygen at the *para*-position of the morpholine ring, rapid transformation into T_2 may be envisaged from which the leaving group departs quickly forming the products 2 and 3. Use of aprotic media further facilitates decomposition of the intermediate complex. Correlation with solvent polarity parameter⁴, E_T (30) (Table 1)

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT (k_A) FOR THE REACTIONS OF 1 WITH MORPHOLINE IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

[Substrate] = 4.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 35 ± 0.1°

Solvent	10^{-3} [Nu] mol dm ⁻³	$10^{-2} k_A$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	E_T (30)	α	β
Toluene	1.40	13.70	33.9	0	0.11
	1.65	13.66			
	2.20	13.72			
	2.85	13.97			
	3.31	13.80			
Benzene	2.45	13.88	34.3	0	0.10
	3.00	13.71			
	3.30	13.91			
	3.90	13.89			
	4.40	14.16			
THF	22.0	16.67	37.4	0	0.55
	31.0	16.67			
	33.0	16.37			
	39.0	16.12			
	44.0	16.34			
Ethylacetate	55.0	16.78	38.1	0	0.45
	1.30	30.19			
	1.65	29.89			
	1.95	30.39			
	2.65	29.87			
Acetonitrile	3.85	30.40	45.6	0.19	0.31
	1.20	53.50			
	1.65	53.85			
	2.20	51.76			
	2.75	56.63			
3.31	54.76				

exists. A plot of $\log k_A$ vs E_T (30) was linear. However, deviation was observed with solvents having high hydrogen bond acceptor basicity values (β values), such as ethyl acetate and THF. These solvents seem to interact with intermediate complex through hydrogen bonding more effectively. Similar behaviour was reported by Mancini *et al.*⁵ for the reaction of 2,4-dinitrochlorobenzene with piperidine in nitromethane and chloroform although in their case deviations were observed in solvents with hydrogen bond donor properties.

Experimental

Cyclopentadiene-maleic anhydride adduct was converted to the corresponding *N*-hydroxy compound (2) and the latter was converted to compound 1 as per procedure given elsewhere^{1,3}. The reactions of 1 with morpholine were studied in acetonitrile, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, benzene and toluene using five different amine concentrations under pseudo-first order conditions at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The reactions were followed at 363 nm corresponding to the λ_{max} of *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)morpholine directly in the thermostatted quartz cuvette of a Shimadzu UV 2100 spectrophotometer.

N-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)morpholine (3) and 2,3-[cyclop-

enten-3',5'-diyl]-*N*-hydroxysuccinimide (2) were obtained as products in quantitative yields and were characterised by comparison of their R_f values, m.p. and electronic spectral data with those of the authentic samples.

References

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